

Leveraging Quantum Uncertainty: Quantum Randomness Through the Lens of Classical Communication Network[★]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Quantum Randomness
Randomness Testing
Quantum Random Number Generators
Message Authentication Code
One Time Passwords
Quantum Communication Network

ABSTRACT

The generation of random numbers and the study of its properties have been an elusive field for a fair portion of the century. The application of random numbers is employed in many use cases such as cryptography, neural networks, numerical simulation, and gambling. The performance of each of these use cases is profoundly impacted by the employed random numbers; henceforth, the quality of randomness is of critical importance when it comes to their usage. A poorly generated random number can make a security system vulnerable, or any numerical or statistical evaluation misleading. Although various modes of classical random number generators exist and still function to provide strong cryptographic properties, emergence of quantum mechanical randomness has shed light on a novel path of generating certified randomness which supersedes the classical counterpart in terms of security. Harnessing quantum mechanical phenomena enables generation of true random numbers which can be certified and further implemented to elevate the net quality of the specific use cases. In this work, we generate and analyze random numbers from three different sources — 50:50 beam splitter (BS), quantum key distribution (QKD) setup with classical post-processing scheme, and a commercially available quantum random number generator (QRNG) (ID Quantique (IDQ)). The quality of the generated random numbers from the various sources is checked in statistical tests and compared. Further on, we have developed a system which implements the QRNG-based random numbers to facilitate message authentication code (MAC) and one time password (OTP) protocols, demonstrating a communication network application. In this manner we discuss about a network which integrates quantum mechanics to the current classical networking approaches to enhance certain aspects of the networking protocol — in this case, the security.

1. Introduction

Randomness has garnered popularity in numerous fields of research; the study and analysis of which have been a well sought-after topic. The application of randomness has been proven to be pivotal in many fundamental aspects of statistical modelling, cryptography, numerical simulations, gambling, and also in artificial intelligence (AI). Authors

here separates any other form of randomness from quantum randomness with the usage of word "classical." Classical randomness, in its premature stage (1919 [35]), was supported by the first probabilistic theory put forward by von Mises based on the collective property of random sequences [23]. This was based on heuristics as von Mises emphasized probability theory as a physical theory rather than a mathematical theory. Wald [51] and Church [11] further extended the work and developed theorems to satisfy von Mises's theory, which was later on countered by Ville [50]. He argued that a sequence should be considered random if it passes all the possible tests for randomness, forwarding his "typicality" approach. On the other hand, Kolmogorov approached randomness in the context of complexity where complexity was determined algorithmically [26]. Martin-Löf theorem identified the drawbacks of Kolmogorov complexity theorem as it proved that Kolmogorov random sequences do not exist [23]. An improved definition of Kolmogorov concept was developed known as Kolmogorov-Chaitin randomness which referred to incompressible sequences. Further extending the discussion regarding devising measures to quantify randomness, the seminal work of Shannon [44] approached the definition of randomness with a close accordance with Kolmogorov's approach. In terms of information theory, Shannon framed the concept of randomness with "entropy,"

^{*}This work has been partially funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) as part of Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC2050/1 – Project ID 390696704 – Cluster of Excellence "Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop" (CeTI) of Technische Universität Dresden. The authors also acknowledge the financial support by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research of Germany in the programme of "Souverän. Digital. Vernetzt.". Joint project 6G-life, project identification number: 16KISK001K. The work of author Ricardo Pousa as an observer was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101073265(EWOC). Authors, Stefan Krause and Kay-Uwe Giering acknowledges the received funding from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and from the state budget passed by the Saxon state parliament, reference numbers 100498890, 100498868 and 4-7324/27/3-2022/32856.

The authors also extends their gratitude to Felix Kunzmann for data acquisition and Christian Skubich for providing valuable pointers and for discussions. And last but not least, the authors also thank Leonardo A. Gonzalez Z. for his assistance in editing the manuscript.

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H . H signifies the measure of information, choice, and the associated uncertainty; written as following

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log p_i. \quad (1)$$

This is the expectation value of the information content $-\log p_i$ of the various states i , which occur with probability p_i . The entropy equation provides crucial insights for the measure of choice or information. If one is certain of an outcome H vanishes, and is otherwise positive. For a given n , H is maximum surmounting to $\log n$, when all the probabilities (p_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are equally distributed, i.e. $1/n$; which signifies maximum uncertainty.

Previously described chronological developments in the attempt to study randomness were foundational in giving an interpretation towards understand randomness. It can be summarised that in the perspective of classical approach, a random sequence is defined in terms of its 1) unpredictability (von Mises), 2) complexity-incompressibility (Kolmogorov, Solomonoff, Chaitin), and 3) typicality (Martin-Löf) [23]. Khrennikov [23] catalogues von Neumann's monograph [37] about the intrinsic nature of quantum randomness which shifted the paradigm in terms of randomness analysis. His view on classical randomness was that it is reducible to ensemble variations. According to von Neumann, quantum randomness exhibits the violation of causality. Indeterminism and randomness became commonly accepted properties of quantum mechanics as postulated by Born, Heisenberg, and Pauli [9]. Since then, quantum randomness have been pitched as to be a phenomena birthed from the effect of device-induced measurement of the quantum state, as famously described by Heisenberg's Gedanken experiment [15]. This view supported the local hidden variable model where the real states are hidden at microscopic levels and are irreversibly lost to the large scale world. With a matured theoretical and experimental demonstration of violation of Bells inequality, the disapproval of local hidden variable models has been demonstrated [5, 43]. The violation of Bell's inequality is an essential criteria that modern day QRNG comply with, this will be discussed briefly in later sections.

Relying on classical processes to generate randomness gives rise to *epistemic* randomness — implying a lack of detecting any significant regularities in the events [9]. If one knows enough about the system configuration or its evolution, then the outcomes can be completely predicted. On the contrary, quantum randomness have been credited with *objective* randomness because of its physical process which gives rise to inherent randomness — even if the initial state is known, observed value during measurement is still indeterministic.

The transition from classical randomness to quantum randomness has presented many mathematical rigours for understanding randomness in general. Although, quantification of what *truly random* means is still open for discussion. As mentioned in [10] randomness is an asymptotic

property which results in difficulty in conducting a randomness test [10]. Moreover, relying on classical phenomena such as chaotic systems [47], thermal noise [54], cosmic background radiation [29], etc, for randomness generation provides promise but is limited in certifying the source of randomness. Whereas quantum randomness, with the intrinsic nature of unpredictability, can be certified of its randomness [2, 1] and can produce randomness which is true in nature.

There have been many testaments in the past that have displayed how security threats are welcomed by the predictability and the poor quality of randomness. Infamous disclosure of U.S. national security agency (NSA) by Edward Snowden was particularly in this direction[34]. The disclosure exposed the backdoor NSA had created using dual elliptic curve deterministic random bit generator (Dual EC DRBG) which enabled them to crack several cryptographic keys. The Dual EC DRBG was later ruled out by national institute of standards and technology (NIST). Another sophisticated attack was carried out in 2010 on the PS3 console, which exploited the ECDSA algorithm that was employed by Sony. The attack unveiled Sony's negligence in using the same key multiple times for authentication [14]. In 2013, Google reported in [25] about the improper initialization of underlying pseudo random number generator (PRNG) in Android devices which supported the java cryptographic architecture (JCA) for key generation, signing, and random number generation. This shortcoming resulted into updation of multiple Bitcoin application. A plethora of such examples exist in past which have been served as an evidence to poorly generated random numbers. It will not be wise to believe that existing random number generator (RNG)s that depend on classical physics will not be predicted by a more mature algorithm of the future; for instance, it was believed Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) public-key can not be broken in polynomial time, later on Peter Shor's work [45] in devising a method to factorize an integer in polynomial time using a quantum computer disproved it. Therefore, it is imperative to formalise various other methods to produce random numbers which are inherently unpredictable and are true in nature. The communication network of future will not be limited to classical mechanisms, the inclusion of quantum computation and its implication in security is already a direction researchers have planned to take for future 6G networks [40]. Henceforth, the development of various paradigms to integrate the quantum notion in the current classical networking system becomes crucial for near-term classical-quantum networks. This work focuses on the objective primarily.

In this work, we produce random numbers from various quantum mechanical setups and analyse the generated random numbers in terms of its quality. Specifically we have employed a scheme of 50:50 beam splitter and QKD setup to extract random numbers. Additionally, we have also utilized a commercial random number generator, IDQ, from the Quantis company [41] for comparison. The analysis have been done by employing the statistical test

suite (STS) provided by NIST, specifically [4] which is a standardised method to test PRNGs and [48] for validating entropy sources. Additionally, the generated random numbers have also been analyzed on the basis of the autocorrelation coefficient. Subsequently, following the path of mentioned classical-quantum network, we demonstrate a method deploying docker containers to employ procured random numbers in two use cases: MAC and OTP. Both the use cases are heavily utilized in day-to-day life for authentication purposes in a network and they base their proper functioning on the source of RNGs. Realisation of such a classically emulated setup utilizing QRNG in the backend provides crucial insights in integrating quantum principles inside currently available classical networking architecture.

The rest of the article is arranged in the following manner. In Section 2, a brief description about various random number generation techniques and their classification is presented. Section 3 elaborates the experimental setup of the adopted QRNG schemes that have been employed in this work. The details of the analysis of randomness procured from the adopted QRNGs is described in Section 4. Additionally, Section 5 encapsulates the presented proof of concept by employing procured quantum random number (QRN). Finally, Section 6 summarizes the work and discusses future aspects of extending the presented work.

2. Random Number Generators

In this section, we will discuss various modes of RNGs, albeit briefly. A majority of focus will be on the QRNGs which will provide a pathway to further understand our implemented experimental setup in generating quantum random numbers. This section is only limited in describing broader categories of random number generators such as: PRNG, true random number generator (TRNG), and within the category of TRNG, the description of QRNG. For further in depth classification and other sources of RNGs, the authors directs the reader to the review [32].

The quality of a good RNG is credited to its ability to generate unpredictable sequences, the speed with which it generates data (bits/seconds), and its versatility (in terms of its usage in various use cases). The specific use cases often impacts the design and performance of a RNG as some applications demand high speed, where other higher reliability. Historically, deterministic algorithms have been employed to generate strings of numbers which mimic certain properties of random numbers. The usage of deterministic algorithms as a seed to generate random numbers falls under the category of PRNG. For most computational and statistical applications, PRNGs suffices the needs, as they are easy to implement, less complex, faster in practical usage, and bear the potential to generate the same sequence [30]. The latter property is occasionally comes in handy during debugging and verification. Based on L'Ecuyer's framework [28], a generator has a structure $S = (S, s_0, T, U, G)$, where S is a finite set of states, $s_0 \in S$ is the initial state, $T : S \rightarrow S$ is the transition function, U is a finite set

of output, and $G : S \rightarrow U$ is the output function. From the initial state s_0 , which is the seed, the generator outputs a sequence (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_i) ; given, $u_0 := G(s_0)$, $s_i := T(s_{i-1})$, and $u_i := G(s_i)$. The output from such a generator is expected to imitate independent and identically distributed random variables, uniformly distributed over U . A majority of PRNG is based on number theory. For instance, the linear congruential generators by Lehmer [24] which uses the recursive formula $X_{n+1} = (aX_n + b) \bmod m, n \geq 0$. Where, X_i is the i -th digit, which is multiplied by $a(0 \leq a \leq m)$ and is incremented by $b(0 \leq b \leq m)$, and X_{i+1} is obtained using $m \geq 0$ as the modulus. As mentioned earlier the application defines the usage of the deterministic algorithms. The recursive formula becomes vulnerable when it is required for cryptographic applications. Cryptography demands forward and backward security to make any adversarial intrusion impotent. Blum-Blum-Shub [7] is one such legacy generator which harnessed bi-prime factorization problem.

Whereas PRNG has its advantages in being versatile for certain applications, in highly critical security aspects the deterministic algorithms opens up pathway for potential attacks. On the contrary, TRNG rely on physical processes to generate entropy. The physical process can possibly be of any form from the temperature variations of the environment, user's mouse clicks, electronic noises, cursor motion, to the chaotic systems. The UNIX system already harnesses these phenomenons as a source of entropy to provide random numbers. Generated randomness from TRNG leverages our ignorance or inability to model and quantify a particular system. The evaluation of a TRNG is rather difficult as it is complex to differentiate among various noise generated from a physical process, hence, it is practically difficult to certify the entropy source. As previously mentioned, several TRNG employ noise as an entropy source, although, it is a complex task to distinguish whether the noise is of thermal origin or a shot noise which hinders the calculation of entropy. Whereas, QRNG is an unique and special case of TRNG where intrinsic quantum mechanical processes involving atoms are used to generate randomness. It is to be noted that, although shot noise is a form of quantum phenomenon, QRNGs do not utilize it as a source of entropy. Unlike TRNGs (except QRNG) which rely on classical physical processes and merely appear to be completely random, QRNG provides inherent unpredictability. So far, one can safely say that TRNG are hardware based random number generators. Early developments of QRNG was based on radioactive decay of particles [42]. Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is the only tool to understand radioactive decay. Therefore, the generated random numbers do possess the properties of uncertainty and incompatibility. Radioactivity as an entropy source demands intricate care limiting their practicality. Over the course of time, the detectors associated with the setup experience gradual deprivation in its efficiency. All these issues render rather slower generation rate. The group of Anton Zeilinger [20] came up with the very first notion of photon based QRNG. The principle of it is straightforward: a photon generation source (typically a laser) emits a train of

single photons towards a BS which has a certain probability of transmitting or reflecting the impinging single photons. A transmitted and reflected single photon creates a superposition of spatial modes which is further on detected by single-photon detectors. The photon detectors at the output port detects whether a photon was reflected or transmitted, which corresponds to the value '0' or '1' or vice-versa. A schematic of this procedure have been adopted in this work and have been presented in the Section 3 Fig. 1. If this procedure is repeated several times, a string of binary data is generated. However, the instruments involved in the experimental setup experiences some shortcomings such as low detection efficiency and dark counts, which lowers the random number generation rate. A single-photon detector exploiting spatial and temporal distributions can enable the development of high-speed random bit generators. Spatially, by measuring the arrival positions of emitted photon can enable multi random bits per detection of photons [52]. Additionally, it has been shown in the work [39] by implementing special circuitry for converting the exponentially distributed arrival of photons to a uniform one, the generation rate can be increased. Vacuum noise or the zero-point fluctuations of electromagnetic field can also be resorted for generation of random numbers. A speed up to 8.25 Gbps has been reported in [16] utilizing vacuum noise. Measuring the phase fluctuations of the laser by an interferometer with a photodetector a speed-up of 68 Gbps was achieved in [38]. Another interesting concept of device independent (DI) QRNG exists, which abstracts away the hardware dependencies that can be tampered with by an adversary. This is achieved by certifying the source of randomness by Bell inequality violations and is a key principle in generating self-testing QRNG. The mechanism of certification anchors the random bit generation rate and the speed is limited to few Kbps. Although, partial independence — source or measurement device independence, can be a practical trade-off between security and performance. For instance, source independence have potential to generate random numbers with a speed of 17 Gbps [3], whereas measurement device independence can perform up to 16.5 Mbps [8].

3. Experimental Setup

In this section we will describe the procedures that we have adopted to generate random numbers from quantum mechanical phenomena, experimentally.

For different scenarios of generating QRNs, we use an entangled photon source based on a Sagnac loop in which a PPKTP (periodically poled potassium titanyl phosphate) crystal is pumped by a 405 nm single mode diode laser (Topmode 405, Toptica). The crystal is kept at a constant temperature within a crystal oven. The source generates about 200,000 photon pairs per second with a heralding efficiency of about 20%. The photons are polarization entangled and generated in one of the four Bell states with a measured visibility of about 96%.

QRNs are generated by the following approaches. The BS-based QRNs are generated by sending the individual photons of the signal output of our entangled photon source onto a fiber based 50:50 non-polarizing BS (TN808R5F1, Thorlabs) as schematically depicted in Fig. 1. The two BS outputs are then connected to two single photon avalanche diodes (SPADs, SPCM-800-13 FC, Excelitas) which generate an electrical output pulse measured subsequently by a time tagger (quTAG MC, qutools). This approach yields about 600,000 counts/s which are attributed according to their output channel to 0 (b) or 1 (c). At such a low photon stream the entangled photon source output can be considered as a single photon source.

QKD based QRNs are generated by implementing a fully functional QKD setup and extracting the quantum random numbers from the generated key material. BBM92 [6] QKD protocol has been adopted for this very purpose. A scheme of the setup is shown in Fig. 2. The photons of the signal (idler) path are sent to a receiving unit, Alice (Bob), via standard single mode telecommunication fibers and analyzed with respect to their polarization. Therefore, the photons are decoupled from the fiber and impinging on a 50:50 non-polarizing BS cube. Afterwards quarter and half waveplates are verifying that the subsequent projection through a polarizing BS cube takes place in the V/H- or the D/A-base, respectively. The four possible outputs behind the two polarizing BSs are coupled into multi-mode fibers and connected to four single photon avalanche diodes (SPADs). The SPAD signals are then again registered by a time tagger (quTAG MC, qutools). The acquired data is analyzed and photons are associated with each other by cross correlation analysis. The received photon data is then post-processed in a python-based software framework, comprising identification of photon pairs, bit sifting, quantum bit error estimation, error correction, privacy amplification and key export. The generated key material consisting of a random sequence of 0 and 1 is utilized as quantum random numbers. The secure key rate of this setup amounts to about 5 Kbits/s.

The two experimental setups described above employ the Bell state $|\psi_+\rangle = (|HV\rangle + |VH\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$. Measuring this state with two linear polarizers, with angles α, β , respectively, lets the two photons pass the polarizers with probability $|\langle\alpha, \beta|\psi_+\rangle|^2 = 1/2 \cdot \sin^2(\alpha + \beta)$. Hence, the individual polarisation measurements show a) a strong correlation (which is applied in the QKD setup) and b) an isotropy in say α at fixed $\alpha + \beta$ (which can be exploited to generate random numbers). More complex measurement setups employ polarizing BSs, such as Wollaston prisms, instead of polarizing filters. Our first setup, Fig. 1, sends one photon to a 50:50 BS, while disregarding the second pair photon, and generates a superposition state of a reflected and of a transmitted photon. The second setup, Fig. 2, generates a superposition state where different optical paths through the polarization analysis module correspond to different linear polarizations (H, V, D, A). For either setup, the measurement of the spatial position through the single-photon detectors collapses the wave function and thus generates a random

Figure 1: Scheme of a 50:50 non-polarizing BS cube on the left and a fiber based 50:50 non-polarizing BS with a single input and two output ports on the right. In the presented work the signal output of the aforementioned entangled photon source was used to create a stream of individual photons impinging on a fiber-based BS.

number. The relative weights in the superposition states, and hence the probabilities of each random character, depend on the details of the optical setup (coupling efficiencies, properties of the BS, waveplates and Wollaston prisms, quality of Bell state preparation etc.). Whereas the (ideal) 50:50 BS is insensitive to polarization, having (roughly) equal probabilities for photon transmission and reflection, the Wollaston prism relies on the isotropy property of $|\psi_+\rangle$. Hence, in the QKD setup, two different random numbers are generated: the BS behavior leads to a random choice of measurement basis, and the Wollaston prism behavior leads to a random bit which is later on processed to obtain a random quantum key.

In a third experimental setup, we employ a commercial QRNG (Quantis QRNG, IDQ) [41], which is quantum optics based as well, to create data sets of quantum random numbers.

4. Results and Analysis

In this section we have considered several metrics for quantifying the quality of randomness of procured random numbers from various quantum mechanical sources. Initially, the random numbers have been analyzed using the standardised NIST statistical test suite, followed by NIST special publication (SP) 800 – 90B for measuring entropy of various sources. Additionally we have also analyzed the obtained random numbers in terms of autocorrelation.

4.1. NIST STS 800-22

The acquired random numbers from various sources have been tested for randomness using the NIST statistical test suite [4], specifically NIST STS 800 – 22. The statistical test suite is based on null hypothesis testing. The verification of the null hypothesis is based on certain characteristics of bits or block of bits. The evaluation of the test utilizes the distribution of the null hypothesis statistics. Generally, NIST STS adopts χ^2 or normal distribution as reference distribution. The analyzed statistics is then transformed into p -value. In NIST STS 800 – 22, there are 15 randomness

tests with several tests having further sub tests. Implementing the entire test suite demands a particular sequence to contain at least 100000 bits as per NIST guidelines. It is also recommended by NIST that at least 100 sequences should be tested [4]. For this work, 10^6 bits have been assessed in one sequence and a net amount of 200 sequences have been analyzed to provide the p -values as displayed in Table 1, 2, and 3 for the cases of 50:50 BS, QKD setup, and IDQ, respectively. From the results it can be seen that, since QKD setup and IDQ uses post-processing schemes to further uniformly distribute the acquired raw random bits, all the statistical tests were passed. This remarks that, both the generators produced statistically acceptable random numbers. However, 50:50 BS without any hardware bias reduction or whitening process, failed 7 tests as represented in the Table 1. The lack of post-processing resulted in the failure of several tests. NIST STS was able to detect the bias and predictability of the raw data sample collected using 50:50 BS.

4.2. NIST Entropy Evaluation Suite (SP800-90B)

NIST SP 800 – 90 are series of guidance on how to construct and test entropy sources primarily focusing on cryptographic applications [48]. SP 800 – 90B employs a conservative measure of entropy using min-entropy. The min-entropy associated with an independent discrete random variable X with probability $P(X = x_i) = p$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} H_{min} &= \min_{1 \leq i \leq k} (-\log_2 p_i) \\ &= -\log_2 \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} p_i. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If X has min-entropy H_{min} , then the probability of observing any value of X is bound by $2^{-H_{min}}$. It can be seen that, min-entropy gives a lower bound to success probability of guessing an outcome.

In SP 800 – 90B entropy estimation is done by utilizing ten entropy estimators: 1) The Most Common Value Estimate; 2) The Collision Estimate; 3) The Markov Estimate; 4) The Compression Estimate; 5) The t-Tuple Estimate; 6)

Table 1
NIST STS 800 – 22 result for 50:50 BS

Statistical Test	P-Value	Test Result
Frequency	0.000000	X
Block Frequency	0.000002	X
Cumulative Sums	0.000000	X
Cumulative Sums	0.000000	X
Runs	0.000000	X
Longest Run	0.605916	✓
Rank	0.825505	✓
FFT	0.798139	✓
Non Overlapping Template	0.438928	✓
Overlapping Template	0.000000	X
Universal	0.401199	✓
Approximate Entropy	0.000000	X
Random Excursions	0.564983	✓
Random Excursions Variant	0.469408	✓
Linear Complexity	0.224821	✓

Table 2
NIST STS 800 – 22 result for the key material obtained from QKD setup

Statistical Test	P-Value	Test Result
Frequency	0.941144	✓
Block Frequency	0.788728	✓
Cumulative Sums	0.911413	✓
Cumulative Sums	0.437274	✓
Runs	0.504219	✓
Longest Run	0.484646	✓
Rank	0.883171	✓
FFT	0.805569	✓
Non Overlapping Template	0.489618	✓
Overlapping Template	0.153763	✓
Universal	0.668321	✓
Approximate Entropy	0.689019	✓
Random Excursions	0.290022	✓
Random Excursions Variant	0.437565	✓
Linear Complexity	0.825505	✓

Table 3
NIST STS 800 – 22 result for IDQ

Statistical Test	P-Value	Test Result
Frequency	0.108791	✓
Block Frequency	0.213309	✓
Cumulative Sums	0.4151915	✓
Runs	0.064822	✓
Longest Run	0.017912	✓
Rank	0.514124	✓
FFT	0.779188	✓
Non Overlapping Template	0.480422	✓
Overlapping Template	0.153763	✓
Universal	0.668321	✓
Approximate Entropy	0.689019	✓
Random Excursions	0.423108	✓
Random Excursions Variant	0.464611	✓
Serial	0.825505	✓
Linear Complexity	0.825505	✓

Figure 2: Scheme of the experimental setup with Alice on the left side and the entangled photon source (EPS) on the right side. Alice consists of a polarization analysis module built from a non-polarizing BS, quarter and half wave plates (QP,HP), wollaston prisms (WP) and fiber couplers (FC). The polarization resolved photons are guided through multi mode fibers to SPAD for detection. The resulting electronic signal is converted into a digital time stamp by a time tagger (TT) and analysed by a home written software running on a control and analysis computer (C). The EPS consists of a 405 nm pump laser (L), a quarter and half wave plate (QP,HP), a dichroic mirror (DM), a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), mirrors (M), periodically poled potassium titanyl phosphate as the optical active element (ppKTP), long pass filters (LP) and fiber couplers (FC). The polarization transformation of the photons in the fiber is compensated by polarization controllers (PC).

Table 4
Min-entropy estimation using NIST SP 800 – 90B

QRNG	Min-Entropy
50:50 BS	0.909831
QKD setup	0.941550
IDQ	0.938093

The longest repeated substring (LRS) Estimate; 7) The Multi Most Common in Window Prediction Estimate; 8) The Lag Prediction Estimate; 9) The MultiMMC Prediction Estimate; and 10) The LZ78Y Prediction Estimate. The min-entropy is then the minimum value among these ten values. For each of the cases of QRNG the min-entropy has been displayed in Table 4. It can be observed that, the QKD setup has the highest entropy among other QRNG. The enhanced entropy of QKD setup can be credited to the effort put in post-processing which involves various techniques to obtain a uniform distribution of random numbers.

4.3. Autocorrelation

The extracted data from various quantum entropy sources have been put under mathematical transformation to observe the random features. One convenient mathematical tool is of analysing the autocorrelation coefficient $A(k)$, where $A(k)$ is defined as following

$$A(k) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-k} (x_i - \hat{x})(x_{i+k} - \hat{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \hat{x})^2}. \quad (3)$$

Here, x_i is the string of random number sample and x_{i+k} is its shifted counterpart with a delay of k . \hat{x} is the mean value. For our case $n = 10^6$ raw data samples have been taken from each of the quantum sources mentioned in Section 3. The autocorrelation has been plotted in Fig. 3.

In normal y -axis, the analyzed bits had no autocorrelation. Changing the axis to a log scale, unveiled certain correlations in the order ranging between 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} . The autocorrelation coefficient can never drop to zero due to the practical limitations of the instruments involved in the experimental setup — detectors, photon source, post-processing schemes, etc. Although, it can be seen from the plot in Fig.3, QKD setup has lower correlations than any other mode of QRNG signifying its potential in obtaining true random bits.

5. Proof of Concept

In this work, we also aimed to formalize a path to amalgamate quantum and classical aspects for the communication network of the future. We have realized a proof

Figure 3: Autocorrelation between bits and their lagged version for various cases of QRNGs.

of concept which utilizes the generated QRNs in a classical networking architecture. Targeting specifically the use case of security, we have formed a system model using classical emulation tool to include the quantum randomness generation scheme in the architecture. Specifically we have chosen the application of MAC and OTP to demonstrate our purpose. We emphasize on these two use cases because both rely on a secret key. For a secret key to be secure, the entropy is critical. Therefore, we implement the randomness obtained from the QRNG to produce high quality and secure keys.

Message authentication, in general, is a method to establish communication between two parties, where the concerning parties can communicate information knowing that they are genuine. The development of MAC was to enable the transmission of information through a hostile environment, where the eavesdropper can alter, record, and re-transmit the information. It is a layer of security added on top of error correcting codes to provide cryptographic strength. To facilitate a secure communication under MAC, the necessary criteria [21] are: 1) Any form of modification of a message is detectable by the receiver, be it insertion, deletion, or modification of the true contents. 2) Receiver's ability to detect modification of the sequence of messages in a session. Further on, to avert undetectable removal or loss of messages in a session. 3) To permit authentication of message source and destination. If the key used in transmitting the information from A to B is also used in transmitting information from B to A , messages might be reverted back to A even though source was B . Valid messages from C to A might be duplicated and sent as though it had originated from B . 4) The timeliness of the messages should be verified to ensure that a session contains only the current messages and not a replay of an older session. 5) The sender should be able to detect fraudulent acknowledgement of message receipt or non-receipt by someone other than the genuine recipient. MAC have been a reliable mode for verifying the integrity of transmitted information between

two parties[27]. The authentication utilizing MAC begins initially between two parties by sharing a secret key. A MAC, $MAC = (KG, tag, VRFY)$ consists of three algorithms with associated key space \mathcal{K} , message space \mathcal{M} , and tag space \mathcal{T} [13]. KG or Key Generation, here is a probabilistic algorithm $k \leftarrow KG(1^\lambda)$, where λ is a security parameter taken as an input and outputs a secret key $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Tagging or tag , is a probabilistic authentication algorithm $\alpha \leftarrow tag_k(m)$ that takes a message $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and a secret key $k \in \mathcal{K}$ and outputs a MAC tag or authentication tag. Verification or $VRFY$ is a deterministic algorithm $VRFY(m, \alpha)$ that intakes a secret key $k \in \mathcal{K}$, a message $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and a tag $\alpha \in \mathcal{T}$ and outputs a decision: $\{accept, reject\}$.

For our specific demonstration, Keccak message authentication code (KMAC) [22] has been used. KMAC is a keyed hash function and pseudo random function based MAC. KMAC has two variants, KMAC128 and KMAC256 representing the output tag size in bits. The KMAC function $KMAC(K, X, L, S)$, takes four parameters. K is the key of appropriate bit string as recommended by NIST. X is the input bit string or message, of arbitrary length. L is an integer representing the requested output length in bits. S is an additional parameter to customize the length of bit string. QRNG has been the source of entropy to generate keys required by the KMAC function.

In order to extend the analysis to a full-proof authentication system we have also employed OTP authentication which also relies on QRNG-based entropy source for generating human-readable OTPs. OTP authentication is designed to counter passive attacks such as replay attacks. Equivalent to KMAC, generation of OTPs also rely on a secure key known to the token and validation service. OTP system's security is crucially dependent upon the non-invertability of a secure hash function [17]. A HMAC-based one time password (HOTP) algorithm has been implement using the guidelines provided in [36]. As the name suggests, it uses a hash based MAC to generate a hash, which is further decomposed into a easy-to-read number based OTP. HOTP is counter based, i.e. the token generation and validating unit must use this counter to synchronize among themselves so as to validate the right OTP. These protocols are heavily employed in carrying out a transaction and online authentication. A system model accommodating a QRNG has been presented in Fig. 4 which generates keys that is used by the MAC and OTP units. In Protocol 1 a simplified protocol has been presented describing the entire authentication scheme broadly. Upon client's request to get an OTP, the server first tries to authenticate the client by a specific tag. The tag is generated using prior shared key. If the verifying function validates the authenticity of the client then the server proceeds further to generate the requested OTP.

NGINX was used for load balancing and cohesive exposure of the REST API emulating a real scenario, Flask was used for backend implementation of the REST API due to its quick integration with the base implemented simulated quantum modules in Python, and MongoDB was chosen for ease of insertion and removal of data to store previously

Figure 4: The figure showcases the experimental proof of concept implemented, emulating a real scenario of multiple clients through a REST API requesting OTPs from a centralized server.

sent requests. Alpine Linux was used as the base image for every container except MongoDB and NGINX, where the latest publicly available images were used instead. Alpine linux was chosen due to its lightweight nature, enabling the creation of multiple lightweight clients enabling the testing of brute force attacks specifically targeting the random number generation algorithm. Testing the algorithm from the server side is facilitated by the storage of each request in the MongoDB Database for each client. The testing from the client side can be performed by emulating a real-life

scenario from an attacker's perspective. This web-service-like deployment does not seek to implement the full security protocol associated with each of the algorithms exposed, but instead enables further testing on an as-close-to-reality scenario. Therefore Database storage is done without hashing the contents of the message sent to the client, and the messages are exchanged without encryption of its contents.

Screenshots of the OTP and MAC requests and their verification have been displayed in Fig. 5, 6, 7, and 8. In a study carried out in [12], the authors attempted to analyze

(a) OTPs generated using the system model presented in Fig.4.

(b) Plot obtained from [12] showcasing OTPs obtained from Google. Symbols '+' and 'x' represents one and two occurrences of the same OTP, respectively.

Figure 9: Comparison of 6-digit OTPs obtained from the presented system model with OTPs procured from a Google server as reported in [12]. The OTPs are segmented in two halves and are plotted in x- and y-axis. For instance an OTP "121456" is plotted as $x = 121$ and $y = 456$.

can aid in a use case. Focusing solely on the quantum modes of entropy generation, we employed two in-house experimental setups of QRNG and a proprietary QRNG. For our specific consideration, we did not include the analysis of semi-self-testing QRNGs [31], because of their slow nature of random number generation. However, we have analyzed a QKD-based QRNG which is a self-testing QRNG because even if the devices are compromised the random numbers obtained will be true in nature. The QKD-based QRNG approach was chosen to compare the quality of randomness with that of IDQ, as both undergoes through a phase of

classical post-processing. Qualifying the NIST tests is not a sign of proof that procured random strings are certified to be truly random; although it consolidates the fact that the amount of observable patterns are greatly reduced for it to be utilized in cryptographic applications. The three methods of random number generation also provides different flavor of quantum technology involved in each of the scheme. The 50:50 BS-based QRNG showcases the single-photon detection technology, where qubits are prepared in superposition and are measured. For our specific case, the bit generation was limited to 0.6 Mbps. QKD-based QRNG was based on the concept of shared randomness between two parties where the random configuration of basis choices creates randomness which further undergoes classical post-processing. The observed bit rate was only 5 Kbits/s. The IDQ PCIe whereas adapted the multiple photon-number state quantum technology. The randomness from such a device results from measuring the quantum states containing multiple photons. IDQ provides a random data output speed of 9.6 Mbps.

Classical post-processing played a crucial role in qualifying NIST tests. We also observed that, merely using a quantum experiment without any post-processing will not generate straight-forwardly bits that are statistically random. The reason behind is the presence of faulty practical functioning of the instruments and the involvement of environmental changes or noise. This claim was supported in NIST SP 800 – 90B entropy analysis and NIST STS 800 – 22 of 50:50 BS-based QRNG. In the case of QKD-based QRNG and IDQ, the statistical tests are almost indistinguishable. Since classical post-processing employs various anti-bias or anti-correlation algorithm to convert an arbitrary sequence of random numbers into uniformly distributed random numbers, it obscures the quantum randomness in the raw sequence and introduces classical noise. It can not be neglected that, in practice, usage of post-processing schemes on a quantum based protocol can further add to latency. Randomness testing is computationally intensive, mainly testing for the existence of long-range correlations. The complexity exponentially increases as number of possible testing patterns increases with patterns length. Therefore, a quantum certification scheme, similar to [19], needs to be implemented to conduct specific tests locally in realistic execution times.

In overall randomness tests QKD-based setup stood out only marginally in comparison to IDQ. Whereas in terms of random number generation, IDQ is significantly faster than any of the analyzed QRNG. IDQ and the 50:50 BS-based QRNG produces local randomness, whereas QKD-based QRNG produces shared randomness. As development of 5G and beyond communication network gaining momentum, the security aspect linked to the services it might provide is becoming extremely crucial. An interesting model, integrating QKD in current classical network has been presented in [33] to demonstrate a network for the post-quantum era. In such a scenario, shared randomness will hold great potential to strengthen the links between nodes.

In our experimental setup, we observed a key exchange rate of 5 Kbits/s. However, for intensive applications, where one would require higher key-generation rates, hardware-based acceleration [53] can catalyze the method of post-processing in QKD systems. Although, QKD is a key establishing protocol and does not necessarily provide authentication, digital signatures or certificates. But in a network model presented in [33], one can also use the already set up QKD links to generate random numbers and further forward it to the key management systems. Another interesting approach to utilize various quantum entropy sources would be to taking an \oplus (XOR) of all generated random strings to form a unique random string, which is provided as a service to the clients [18]. In similar direction, Entropy-as-a-Service [49] principle was proposed to provide conventional computing devices with high-quality alternate entropy to bolster the quality of security. Such a service can assist devices which are unable to produce sufficient quantity or quality of entropy, locally. In Entropy-as-a-Service, the clients need to trust the authority of the server distributing the random numbers. To be unconstrained from such a situation, protocols like [46] can be implemented. For future work, we aim to establish a fully functioning QRNG-based entropy system model, where the random numbers are generated and distributed in a manner that fulfils all the security criteria discussed within this work. Such a system model will be integrated in a fully-functioning 5G network, where various applications utilize the QRNG-based service in an efficient manner.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Siddharth Das: Conceptualization of this study, Data curation, Writing - Original draft preparation, Software, Visualization, and Editing. **Stefan Krause:** Methodology, Experimentation, and Writing. **Kay-Uwe Giering:** Methodology, Experimentation, Writing, and Editing. **Ricardo J.B. Pousa:** Simulation, Software, Writing, and Investigation. **Riccardo Bassoli:** Supervision and Review. **Frank H.P. Fitzek:** Supervision and Review.

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